

**PROBLEMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE
ENTREPRENEURSHIP ON THE BASIS OF THE MARKETING SYSTEM IN
THE FRAMEWORK OF THE ANTI-CRISIS PROGRAM.**

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Bazarova Mamlakat Supievna

Asian International University.

Senior Lecturer, Department of Economics.

Leila Kadyrova

MM-5 group students Iqt 22.

Annotation

In this article, within the framework of the program of anti-crisis measures, the problems of developing small businesses and private entrepreneurship are considered on the basis of a marketing system, business organization and legal documents guaranteeing it, a system of financial support for small businesses in Uzbekistan, analytical information is presented on the problems faced by small businesses and private entrepreneurs and how to effectively use marketing services in solving these problems.

Kalit so'zlar

Small business, medium and small production, financial security, tax system and customs policy, guerrilla marketing, "low-cost" marketing, investment minimization, marketing activities.

Small business is one of the leading sectors of the economy, which largely determines the pace of economic growth, the country's regional development, the state of employment, the structure and quality of the gross national product. The development of small business meets global trends in the formation of a flexible mixed economy, involves a combination of different forms of ownership and an adequate economic model, which implements a complex synthesis of a competitive market mechanism and state regulation of large, medium and small production.¹³¹

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https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Nozim-Muminov/publication/343822220_REGULIROVANIE_DEATELNOSTI_SUBEKTOV_MALOGO_PREDPRINIMAT_ELSTVA_V_NACALE_XXI_VEKA_MIROVOJ_OPYT_Mezdunarodnaa_kollektivnaa_monografiyaTomsk_Izdatelskij_Dom_Tomskogo_gosudarstvennogo_universiteta_2020-332s-/links/5f42f41692851cd3022231f0/REGULIROVANIE-DEATELNOSTI-SUBEKTOV-MALOGO-PREDPRINIMATELSTVA-V-NACALE-XXI-VEKA-MIROVOJ-OPYT-Mezdunarodnaa-kollektivnaa-monografiyaTomsk-Izdatelskij-Dom-Tomskogo-gosudarstvennogo-universiteta-2020-332s.pdf

World practice convincingly shows that even in countries with a developed market economy, small business has a significant impact on the development of the economy, the solution of social problems, and an increase in the number of employed workers. In some countries, small and medium-sized enterprises, in terms of the number and share in the production of goods, the performance of work, and the provision of services, occupy a dominant position compared to large ones. It is noteworthy that scientists from five countries, such as Russia, Ukraine, Tajikistan, China and Uzbekistan, took part in the study. The territory of these countries occupies about 20% of the world's land, the population is more than 20% of the total population of the earth, the total GDP is 18.2% of world GDP.

One of the main goals of establishing a socially oriented market economy in Uzbekistan is the priority development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the country. To realize this goal, economic reforms were carried out, large institutional bases were created to increase its role. These include the organization of business activity and the legal and regulatory documents that guarantee it, non-governmental organizations and enterprises that help entrepreneurs. The establishment of a complex of private entrepreneurship and small business enterprises in Uzbekistan is progressing successfully.

The improvement of the financial support system for small enterprises in Uzbekistan should be carried out in the direction of stimulating the activities of banks, funds, investment and insurance organizations serving small business and private entrepreneurship. As in foreign countries, in the Republic of Uzbekistan, if the enterprise is participating in a priority state program (creation of new equipment, development of remote areas, etc.), it can receive preferential loans. In this case, the minimum rate of interest and the provision of a long period for breaking off the debt are the main conditions for lending.

As a result of the measures taken aimed at further improving the business support system and improving the business climate, on the basis of resolutions and decrees adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the attention paid to this area, in January-March 2019-2023, a total of 127 781 small enterprise and microfirm. It should be noted that the largest number of new entities was created in the field of trade - 49 048 (or 38.4%), services - 28 416 (or 22.2%), industry - 24 612 (or 19.3%), agriculture, forestry and fisheries - 16 605 (or 13.0%), construction - 9 100 (or 7.1%).¹³²

¹³² file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/9.Small%20business.pdf

Main indicators of small business (January-March)

	<i>unit of measurement</i>	2022	2023	(+/-)
Number of operating small enterprises and microfirms	units	475 465	417 216	-58 249
Newly created	units	23 977	23 230	-747
<i>The share of small business in:</i>				
GDP	%	44,5	43,7	-0,8
industry	%	21,6	28,4	6,8
agriculture, forestry and fisheries	%	97,1	96,1	-1,0
investments	%	54,1	58,1	4,0
construction	%	76,5	76,6	0,1
retail trade	%	83,4	82,8	-0,6
services	%	51,2	46,8	-4,4
transportation of goods	%	38,9	43,5	4,6
cargo turnover	%	66,4	69,7	3,3
transportation of passengers	%	92,1	92,9	0,8
passenger turnover	%	94,2	95,2	1,0
export	%	15,6	25,3	9,7
import	%	49,0	48,4	-0,6

A number of problems in the field of small business and private entrepreneurship are visible in Uzbekistan. We will study such problems one by one. According to international experts, the tax system and customs policy are among the problems that should be solved first. The head of our country has developed a number of preferential programs to support entrepreneurship, in which special attention is paid to tax and customs benefits. But despite such measures, some of these programs are not implemented on time by higher organizations, and as a result, the existence of various administrative command systems has a negative impact on this situation.

We believe that one of the other problems is that Uzbekistan should actively participate in the international division of labor and the chain of global added value creation, liberalize the currency market and introduce free conversion. Uzbekistan's competitiveness can increase if small enterprises in the country have more narrow specialization, and large ones start to operate on a large scale. This allows them to improve, minimize downtime and increase the quality of products. It would be appropriate to establish a long value-added chain and reform the tax system that hinders the consolidation of companies.¹³³

¹³³ <https://www.gazeta.uz/oz/2017/01/12/biznes/>

Small businesses and private entrepreneurs face another problem that requires special analyzes and specialists. That is, qualified marketers to analyze the situation of small business and private business entities in the market, the behavior of consumers, the organizational behavior of competitors, their activity in the foreign and domestic markets, as well as the demand and supply for the products of business entities, the form and methods of sales there is a need to conduct research.

In the conditions of market relations, the effectiveness of the marketing system becomes a decisive factor in the viability of economic entities. At the same time, there is an increase in the intensity of the emergence of crisis phenomena in the modern economy, which leads to a reduction in both the management and marketing budgets of modern companies, and makes the optimization of the marketing activities of business entities, in particular, small businesses, of particular relevance. In the process of improving the effectiveness of the marketing system, one of the key tasks is the design of the mechanism of marketing communications.¹³⁴

In the context of the economic crisis, "guerrilla marketing", which the authors also call "low-budget", "low-cost" marketing, is becoming increasingly popular. In low-budget marketing we will understand the whole range of actions to interact with the market in accordance with the strategy of minimizing investment in marketing activities or in conditions of an insufficient number of personnel, a limited marketing budget, or less in relation to similar companies. This strategy can be effective primarily for small firms operating in the market according to the principles by which the guerrillas fight. Instead of "heavy weapons" (expensive advertising media), "light weapons" (low-budget advertising or other elements of the promotion complex) are used.

In conclusion, we can say that small businesses and private entrepreneurs in this case can use low-budget technologies and traditional marketing communications tools. This can be done with low-budget and extra-budgetary funds.

Table 1

Technologies and tools of low-budget MK.

Technology	Technology characteristic	Instrumental
Viral Marketing	Methods of advertising distribution by generating information through a bright, creative idea.	- video clips, video files, flash games; - multimedia postcards; - entertainment micro-sites, online services; - viral activity in the social. networks

¹³⁴ <https://earchive.tpu.ru/bitstream/11683/48368/1/TPU558928.pdf>

Buzz marketing (including rumor marketing, WOM, word of mouth)	Spreading information through artificially created rumors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - teaser campaign, that is, an advertising construction in the form of a riddle, which contains part of the information about the product, but the product itself is not shown; - recommendations; - "life placement" - the introduction of goods into everyday life using fictitious "happy customers".
Low budget advertising	The way to attract the attention of consumers with the lowest financial costs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - advertising in newspapers free ads; - advertising on forums and free portals on the Internet; - use of objects of the surrounding and own areas as an advertising medium; - graffiti advertising on walls and asphalt; - advertising in social networks.
Joint Marketing	Co-marketing - joint management of a single complex process aimed at achieving common goals and objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - joint promotion, conducting cross-promotions with partners, joint events with suppliers; - joint participation in exhibitions
Low-budget public relations	Formation of mutually beneficial relationships between consumers and producers, based on low-cost marketing techniques	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - speaking in the press as an expert, writing articles for thematic magazines, sending out press releases; - speeches at conferences and meetings of public and professional organizations; - organization of round tables; - work in social messengers, corporate blogging, website; - flash mobs and internal corporate PR.
low budget direct marketing	Establishing effective feedback based on long-term direct relationships with each consumer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - postal and electronic mailings; - QR codes, i.e. a two-dimensional bar code (bar code) that provides information for its quick recognition using a camera on a mobile phone.
Low-budget sales promotion	Development of effective marketing promotion programs with a limited budget	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - games, auctions, competitions; - participation in promotions held by retailers.

Based on the above considerations, we would like to make the following suggestions and recommendations to solve the problems of development of small business and private business entities based on the marketing system.

First, effective use of low-cost methods for marketing research by small businesses and private entrepreneurs. For example, social networks can be a clear example of this.

Second, effective use of effective marketing strategies. In the process of applying these strategies, the use of the services of marketers, for example, outsourcing, outsourcing and freelancing services is considered to be of particular importance in this process.

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